

**STAGES OF ACHIEVING HIGH PRODUCTIVITY THROUGH THE USE
OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN MANUFACTURING
ENTERPRISES**

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**ISHLAB CHIQARISH KORXONALARIDA INNOVATSION
TEKNOLOGIYALARNI QO'LLASH ORQALI YUQORI
NATIJDORLILIKKA ERISHISH BOSQICHLARI**

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**ЭТАПЫ ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ ВЫСОКОЙ ПРОИЗВОДИТЕЛЬНОСТИ ЗА
СЧЕТ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ НА
ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯХ**

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Abstract: This article analyzes the stages of achieving high efficiency through the use of innovative technologies in manufacturing enterprises. The process of introducing innovative technologies, the necessary training and resources for this, as well as changes within the enterprise are considered. The article discusses the impact of technological changes on production processes, the role of innovative solutions in increasing labor productivity and improving quality.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ishlab chiqarish korxonalarida innovatsion texnologiyalarni qo'llash orqali yuqori natijadorlikka erishish bosqichlari tahlil etiladi. Innovatsion texnologiyalarni joriy etish jarayoni, buning uchun zarur bo'lgan tayyorgarlik va resurslar, shuningdek, korxonada o'zgarishlar ko'rib chiqiladi. Maqolada texnologik o'zgarishlarning ishlab chiqarish jarayonlariga ta'siri, mehnat unumdorligini oshirish va sifatni yaxshilashda innovatsion yechimlarning roli haqida muhokama olib boriladi.

Аннотация: В статье анализируются этапы достижения высокой производительности труда за счет использования инновационных технологий на производственных предприятиях. Рассмотрен процесс внедрения инновационных технологий, подготовка и необходимые для этого ресурсы, а также изменения внутри предприятия. В статье рассматривается влияние технологических изменений на производственные процессы, роль инновационных решений в повышении производительности труда и улучшении качества.

Keywords: efficiency, enterprise, national economy, international relations. innovation, competitiveness, employees

Kalit so'zlar: samaradorlik, korxonada, milliy iqtisodiyot, , xalqaro munosabatlar. innovatsiya raqobatbardosh, xodimlar

Ключевые слова: эффективность, предприятие, национальная экономика, международные отношения. инновации конкурентоспособны, сотрудники

"Innovative activity (introduction of innovations) is the process of creating competitive types of products (goods) based on new production technologies. This process includes work from the emergence of an idea, determining its purpose and implementation to organizing production, manufacturing products, selling them and obtaining economic benefits."¹

¹ Kolyvanov V. Yu., Magomedov M. B., Gamidov G. S. Main directions of activating innovation activity in the formation of an innovation economy // Innovations. 2017. No. 4 (102). P. 51-54.

In order for people to take their place in the socio-economic environment, they need to constantly work on themselves, develop, improve their knowledge and skills, strive for innovative activity, implement innovative ideas, and absorb innovations created by others.

In this modern world, the concept of "innovation" refers to the creative renewal and radical change of some type of activity.

The process of changing something existing into a new state or acquiring a new quality is recognized as innovation. This process is sometimes also called the implementation of innovation in practice. Innovations are initially formed in the minds of people as a discrepancy between the existing reality and its ideal state. In most cases, innovative ideas are formed on the basis of an attempt to eliminate internal conflicts between rapidly growing needs and the potential capabilities of a relatively slowly developing production system.

When studying the promotion of innovative activity in industrial enterprises, we believe it is appropriate to substantiate the essence of the concepts of "innovative process", "innovative activity", "innovative field", "innovative project", and "innovative program" and to clarify their differences.

The concept of innovation is broad, and it implies the introduction of advanced, new, previously unknown technologies into the production process.

Innovative activity is understood as the creation of something new that can help radically change processes in the field of economic activity.

The innovation process is a process consisting of interrelated stages that form a single whole, preparing and implementing innovative changes. The innovation process consists of preparing and implementing innovative changes and consists of interrelated elements that form a single whole. As a result of this process, innovation appears. For the implementation of the innovation process, diffusion - the timely distribution of innovations that have been mastered and used once in new conditions and places of application - is of great importance.

An innovation sector is a field of activity that includes producers and consumers of innovative products (works, services), including the creation and dissemination of innovations.

An innovation project is a set of technical, organizational, planning and calculation-financial documents necessary to implement the project goals.

An innovation program is a document that is a complex combination of projects, which, as an object of management, can be a separate project or projects that are very

loosely connected to each other and are implemented by an organization or its executors.

Innovative management - in terms of content and quality, denotes a certain level of management and a specific characteristic of management activities. That is, knowledge, technologies, methods and tools, approaches that have a new characteristic in a given place are included in the methods and tools of management, principles, internal characteristics and features, criteria, conditions or environment considered traditional. It should be noted that innovative management does not always negate or completely replace traditional management.

Innovation management represents the renewal of all aspects of an enterprise's business processes. It includes not only technical or technological developments, but also changes in all aspects of the enterprise's activities for the better, as well as the process of managing new knowledge.

Firstly, the management of the creation of new knowledge was an important impetus for the emergence of innovation management. Initially, the scientific field developed under external influences, responding to the needs of production and human life. Scientific knowledge arose spontaneously, was not controlled, and its effectiveness decreased over time. The period of the qualitative development stage of the scientific field begins in the middle of the 20th century, when "Science is about science". Managers became full-fledged participants in research work, science partially turned to consumers. Science begins to act as a logical continuation of the emergence of research processes.

The current era requires the field of science to sharply turn towards the consumer. The creation of new knowledge requires monitoring of consumers in the implementation of management.

Secondly, the management of the potential of creators of new economic knowledge is characterized by the huge amount of knowledge accumulated in the 21st century. Even on narrow topics, decisions are made and implemented in large quantities, at various levels and in various forms, and many methods are used. A huge flow of information circulates. An individual specialist cannot cover even a narrow range of available information, while humanity continues to accumulate information at a rapid pace. In addition, many practical decisions are made as a result of the application of knowledge and experience in other areas.

Today, it is not difficult to understand the need to create special methodologies for searching for new knowledge at low cost and achieving the goal with high

probability. The demand for managing the creative potential that creates new knowledge is growing.

Thirdly, it is necessary to manage the assimilation of innovations, to implement innovations found in technology, economics, and in general in all areas of activity. The introduction of innovation has always been an urgent and acute problem in our country. Such a problem is associated with the abstraction of a positive result, that is, with its manifestation. Therefore, it is necessary to carry out systematic and large-scale work to develop the management of the introduction of innovation.

Fourthly, managing the social and psychological aspects of innovation: accelerating the introduction of innovations and expanding their scope creates a strong conflict between the old and the new. The psychological aspect of “replacing the old with the new” sometimes becomes a strong and insoluble problem, since any innovation should be understood as a sharp turning point in the period of its replacement. Until now, due to the insufficient development of the methodology for predicting development, attention has been paid to the need to introduce innovations only during crises. Currently, advanced companies use a crisis prevention strategy.

Innovation connects sectors with different natures of economic activity and forms of management: science, production, investment, sales of products. By improving the methods and methods of innovation management, quickly adapting to the market situation, developing new areas of equipment use at the enterprise, introducing necessary innovations for management, and improving all elements of modern management that correspond to the characteristics of the market, innovators will be able to successfully use all types of resources in innovation activities.

The implementation of innovation always depends on market demand. To ensure that long-term and short-term programs are balanced, that is, to determine the appropriate approach in the market, to increase the efficiency of innovation potential, the innovation manager determines how much new goods and services to develop, what products are needed for modernization.

Currently, the priority areas of the innovation program at enterprises include the introduction of new products into production, the development of new market segments, increasing the profitability of the enterprise, the optimal use of available material and scientific resources, etc.

It can be said that as a result of the application of scientific and technical developments in the production process, they become products of scientific and technical innovation. The development and implementation of innovations, the

complexity of processes, the emergence of new technologies require the employee to have appropriate qualifications and specific professional knowledge and skills. In innovative structures, the general level of employee education significantly increases. The emerging type of employees requires employees who are able to take responsibility for themselves and make decisions. The delegation of authority and the associated reduction in the powers of higher levels of the organizational hierarchy are closely related to the growth of initiative, personal freedom and efficiency of employees.

The implementation of innovative activities at textile enterprises, one of the leading sectors of the industry of our republic, is characterized by a number of unique features.

Figure 1.2. Features of implementing innovative activities in textile enterprises

First of all, we need to take into account that this industry satisfies the population's need for consumer goods, the wide range of products produced, and the high labor requirements of the industry's products, as well as the high share of raw material consumption in the cost of the product.

Innovation management refers to the renewal of all aspects of an enterprise's business processes. It includes not only technical or technological developments, but also changes in all aspects of the enterprise's activities for the better, as well as the process of managing new knowledge.

Factors influencing innovation activity can be further divided into 2 groups:

1. Factors that hinder innovation activity.
2. Factors that facilitate innovation activity.

Among the economic and technological factors, the following are considered to be factors that hinder innovation activity: lack of funds for financing investment projects; weak material and technical base and outdated technology; lack of reserve capacities; and dominance of existing production interests. The factors that contribute to innovation activity are the financial, material and technical means necessary for economic and scientific and technical infrastructure, the availability of a reserve of progressive technologies, and material incentives for innovation activity.

In conclusion, among socio-psychological and cultural factors, changes in status, the need to look for a new job, the violation of new behavioral stereotypes, resistance to changes that may lead to the violation of established traditions; fear of uncertainty; fear of punishment for failure, resistance to any innovation coming from the outside are factors that hinder innovation activity, while moral encouragement, public recognition; provision of opportunities for self-realization; a positive spiritual environment in the team are factors that contribute to innovation activity.

List of used literature:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 No. PF-60 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026".
2. Turdiyeva M. Features and priority directions of development of innovative processes in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Bulletin of Science and Practice <https://www.bulletennauki.com> T. 7. No. 12. 2022,221-229c.
3. Mukaddas Turdiyeva. Factors of ensuring competitiveness by motivating innovative activities of enterprise employees. Economics: Analyses and forecasts. No. 4 (16) October-December, 2022 p. 101-105.
4. Sayfutdinov M.A. Development of a marketing strategy for garment enterprises: Candidate of Economic Sciences... dis. TSIU. –T.: 2004. -170 p.
5. Xasanova G.D. "Improving the efficiency of innovation activities of industrial enterprises". Candidate of Economic Sciences... dis. TSIU. –T.: 2006. -141 p.
6. Gaipnazarova Z.T. Theoretical foundations of increasing the efficiency of innovative investment. Candidate of Economic Sciences... dis. Tashkent State Technical University. –T.: 2012. -141 p.